

THE COPING SELF-EFFICACY OF STUDENTS LIVING IN BOARDING HOUSES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses. This study utilized the descriptive quantitative research design. One hundred eighty college students from Kabankalan Catholic College completed the Coping Self-efficacy Scale. Results indicated that the participants that had the highest level of coping self-efficacy when grouped according to program cluster were the College of Arts and Sciences. In contrast, the group that got the lowest level of coping self-efficacy was the College of Business and Accountancy, whereas the highest level of coping self-efficacy in terms of sex where the females compared to males. This study showed that the College of Arts and Sciences had a higher level of coping self-efficacy compared to other program clusters. The results of this study implied that the college students of Kabankalan Catholic College experience a moderate level of Coping Self-efficacy, wherein they are left with no alternative but to adapt and become independent while living in the boarding house. The findings of this study implied that for students to improve their coping self-efficacy, they need to pray and practice meditation.

Keywords: *Coping Self-Efficacy, Boarding houses, program cluster, sex, college of education, college of arts and sciences, college of business and accountancy.*

INTRODUCTION

Living in a boarding house is necessary for students who come from far places. One manifestation of this process is leaving the family home and establishing a residence of one's own especially when he/she enters college. This point in an individual's academic life is considered to be a combination of the external and internal stresses from one's surroundings to be successful, goal path, financial stress, social pressure, and concerns about uncertain futures, social problems, and opportunities, thus requiring preparation and focus with often conflicting priorities. As a result, many of the students living in boarding houses' adjustment success depends of the student's adjustment is dependent on their coping practices (Tattao, 2016).

Additionally, students living in boarding houses experience academic and family difficulties. This can be attributed to the fact that living away from home requires a lot of adjustments on the part of the students as well as coping with the novelty of subjects learned in college. Also, comforts are given up and one has to face the rigors of living independently. On the other hand, social area is considered as never a problem because students living in a boarding house gain friends along the way as they interact and relate with their board mates. College students employ both problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies since this is ultimately aimed at reducing or managing the distress that is associated with stressful situations. However, they always utilize emotion-focused coping strategies. This is attributable to the characteristics of adolescents where they are in the process of developing their emotional maturity and tend to do activities that gain approval and acceptance from peers. Furthermore, college students are transitioning from living with their parents to living on their own. A set of novel responsibilities and roles comes into their lives as the students make a move to a new stage (Tattao, 2016).

Self-efficacy is generally known as an expectation deeply linked to a specific task or situation, various studies have shown the existence of a broader belief—that is, basic self-perceived competence in the face of a wide range of demands (Volz et al. 2019).

The current study aimed to examine the level of coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses. This is to provide valuable information for students to realize the importance of coping as they are living on their own. It was also observed that there are only limited number of researchers on this field. Therefore, this study helped fill the gaps in the area and to contribute a deeper understanding of this construct. The researchers believed that the findings of this study were able to present how students can cope with challenges and difficulties.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the students living in boarding houses when grouped according to the:

- 1.1 Sex;
 - 1.2 Academic Program/Program Cluster?
 2. What is the level of coping self-efficacy of the students living in boarding houses?
 3. Is there a significant difference in the level of coping self-efficacy of the students living in boarding houses when grouped according to their demographic profile?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive-comparative research design. It is intended to describe the characteristics or behavior of a particular population in a systematic and accurate fashion (Gall et al. 2003) and to make comparisons of the likeness and differences among phenomena whether certain factors tend to accompany certain conditions (Goodwin & Goodwin, 1996, as cited in Romeyn, 2010). It is based on the objective of determining the level of coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses and to examine the differences among variables. The researchers used the survey method form where a questionnaire will serve as an instrument in collecting the data needed.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were the college students of Kabankalan Catholic College A.Y. 2022-2023. A total of 180 students (48 males and 132 females) were purposively selected to participate. Specifically, participants were selected from the following program cluster: Bachelor of Science in Psychology, Bachelor of Arts in Philosophy, Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Science, English, Math, Filipino, and Physical Education, Bachelor of Science in Business Administration major in Marketing Management and Financial Management, Bachelor of Science in Accountancy, Bachelor of Science in Information Technology. The participants were identified using the snowball sampling technique, which is a non-probability sampling approach in which new units are recruited to form part of the sample by existing units (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized questionnaire to discover the coping mechanism of self-efficacy in Kabankalan Catholic College of first year to third year students living in a boarding house. The researcher used the instrument title Coping Self-Efficacy Scale (CSE) of Chesney et al (2006).

The coping self-efficacy (CSE) scale, a 26-item assessment of one's confidence in engaging in coping behaviors when confronted with problems in life, was the subject of Chesney et al. (2006) into the psychometric properties. The information came from two randomized clinical trials that assessed the effectiveness of the theory-based Coping Effectiveness Training (CET) intervention in alleviating psychological suffering and boosting mood in people managing chronic illness. The 348 participants were sad, HIV-positive, and sex-with-male men. Participants were evaluated before and after the intervention and then randomly allocated to the intervention or comparison conditions. The CSE scale, coping mechanisms, and indicators of social support, psychological discomfort, and well-being were all included as outcome variables. According to their research findings, all three criteria have good internal consistency and test-retest reliability. These components, according to concurrent validity analyses, measure self-efficacy for various forms of coping. The employment of problem- and emotion-focused coping strategies was shown to be associated with residual zed change ratings that were predictive of decreasing psychological distress and increasing psychological well-being over time. The CSE scale offers a tool to monitor changes in CSE over time in intervention studies and gauge a person's perceived capacity to deal with life's obstacles.

Reliability and validity of the study. The CSE scale, coping methods, and measures of social support, psychological distress, and well-being were all included as outcome variables. According to their findings, all three criteria have strong internal consistency and test-retest reliability. According to concurrent validity analyses, these components assess self-efficacy for various ways of coping. Adopting problem- and emotion-focused coping techniques was associated with residual zed change evaluations that predicted decreasing psychological distress and increasing psychological well-being over time. The CSE scale can be used to evaluate changes in CSE over time in intervention studies and assess a person's perceived ability to deal with life's challenges (Chesney et al. 2006).

Data Gathering Procedures

Prior to the administration of the survey, the researchers sent the letter to conduct the study from the researchers' mentor in Research in Psychology 2 subject to the Department Dean of College of Arts and Sciences, College of Education, and College of Business as a gesture of courtesy.

The sample size was 183 students determined through a snowball sampling technique, and 180 responded, the researchers did the survey using questionnaires. The first part of the questionnaire was the participant's name, program cluster, course, year, and sex. The second part is a brief discussion of the coping self-efficacy scale and how to answer it and the third or the last part of the questionnaire, the questionnaire consists of 26 items. Upon the approval of the request, the researchers distributed the questionnaires to those students living in boarding houses. In distributing the questionnaires, the researchers went to their respective classrooms to reach the participants. They were given 15 minutes to answer the survey. The Researchers

encoded, tallied and tabulated the data gathered and was submitted to the statistician for analysis and interpretation.

Data Analysis

The application of statistical tools and the analysis of the data was dependent on the data to be analyzed and the problems formulated. To determine the profile of the participants, frequency, and percentage will be used. In determining if there is a significant difference in the coping self-efficacy of the students living in boarding houses when grouped according to sex and program cluster, a t-test for independent samples and One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used.

The computed mean scores for the coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses were interpreted using the following guide adapted from the main author of the coping self-efficacy scale Chesney, et al (2006):

Mean Range	Interpretation
0-4	Cannot do at all
5-9	Moderately certain can do
10	Certain can do

Results

Table 1.

Demographic profile of the students living in boarding houses.

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	48	26.7
Female	132	73.3
Academic Program/Program Cluster		
College of Business and Accountancy	32	17.8
College of Education	111	61.7
College of Arts and Sciences	37	20.6
Total	180	100.0

Table 2.
Level of Coping Self-Efficacy of the students living in boarding houses

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Keep from getting down in the dumps.	6.08	1.93	Moderately certain can do
Talk positively to yourself.	7.38	2.08	Moderately certain can do
Sort out what can be changed, and what cannot be changed.	6.58	1.73	Moderately certain can do
Get emotional support from friends and family.	7.43	2.17	Moderately certain can do
Find solutions to your most difficult problems.	7.76	1.85	Moderately certain can do
Break an upsetting problem down into smaller parts.	6.44	1.82	Moderately certain can do
Leave options open when things get stressful.	6.65	1.95	Moderately certain can do
Make a plan of action and follow it when confronted with a problem.	7.02	1.79	Moderately certain can do
Develop new hobbies or recreations.	7.58	2.18	Moderately certain can do
Take your mind off unpleasant thoughts.	6.81	1.92	Moderately certain can do
Look for something good in a negative situation.	7.27	2.31	Moderately certain can do
Keep from feeling sad.	6.06	2.37	Moderately certain can do
See things from the other person's point of view during a heated argument.	5.74	2.17	Moderately certain can do
Try other solutions to your problems if your first solutions don't work.	7.31	2.22	Moderately certain can do
Stop yourself from being upset by unpleasant thoughts.	6.75	1.97	Moderately certain can do
Make new friends.	7.66	2.47	Moderately certain can do
Get friends to help you with the things you need.	7.22	2.31	Moderately certain can do
Do something positive for yourself when you are feeling discouraged.	7.86	1.83	Moderately certain can do
Make unpleasant thoughts go away.	6.72	2.01	Moderately certain can do
Think about one part of the problem at a time.	6.57	1.92	Moderately certain can do

Visualize a pleasant activity or place.	7.10	1.74	Moderately certain can do
Keep yourself from feeling lonely.	6.54	2.30	Moderately certain can do
Pray or meditate.	8.63	1.85	Moderately certain can do
Get emotional support from community organizations or resources.	6.03	2.34	Moderately certain can do
Stand your ground and fight for what you want.	7.67	1.98	Moderately certain can do
Resist the impulse to act hastily when under pressure.	6.49	2.11	Moderately certain can do

Table 3.

Difference Analysis on the level of coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses when grouped according to their demographic profile

Profile	Statistics	Level of Self-Efficacy
Sex	Mean	Male=6.95; Female=6.99
	U-test Coefficient	3013.00
	Probability Value	0.616
	Conclusion	Not Sig.
Academic Program/ Program Cluster	Mean	CBA=6.94, COED=6.95, CAS=7.08
	H-test Coefficient	0.547
	Probability Value	0.761
	Conclusion	Not Sig.

Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of students living in boarding houses which are consisting of 48 males (26.7%) and 132 females (73.3%). Moreover, in the table, the highest number of participants was the College of Education with 111 participants (61.7%) in the sample size.

The table shows that females take the highest number of students living in boarding houses and the College of Education has the highest number of students enrolled at Kabankalan Catholic College in it as visible in the registrar's record of the school. This study is supported by Brilliantes et al. (2022) which revealed that the majority of those residing in boarding houses are female students from distant areas without access to housing.

Table 2 shows the level of coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses. As shown in this table, the top three (3) indicators were as follows: Prayer or meditation, do something positive for yourself when you are feeling discouraged, and find solution to your most difficult problem as indicated in their respective means of 8.63, 7.86, and 7.76. This implies that in times of difficulties they experience in life they first pray to God and ask His guidance so that they can do something positive and find solutions to their problems. This is supported by the findings of the study of Wnuk (2023) which revealed that students who use coping mechanisms including prayer have been shown to have both improved reported mental and physical health as well as improve objectively assessed help outcomes. Furthermore, the study of Fisher (2020) showed that involvement in the community of religious or other local groups as well as offering support to those in need can help students' resilience. Lastly, according to Hao et al. (2020) training in problem solving can be defined as a process that helps a person develop problem solving skills and as a result increase the facility of effective coping. In addition, from a specific viewpoint, problem solving training solves people's difficulties in problem solving.

On the other hand, table 2 shows that the least three (3) indicators were as follows: See things from the other person's view during a heated argument, getting emotional support from community organizations or resources, and keep from feeling sad as indicated in their respective mean of 5.74, 6.03, and 6.06. Even if they receive emotional support from their community organizations or resources, they still cannot avoid being sad because they are alone at home or in their boarding house, and they will still experience homesickness and anxiety. If they are angry, other people's opinions will not help them because their anger is at the forefront, and everything will just fall on deaf ears. This is supported by the findings of the study of Rhokham (2021) which revealed that considering other people's point of view is an intentional process rather than something that is automatic. This implies that the student must work very hard to do it. Moreover, the study of Redman-Maclaren et al. (2019) showed that students are having a poor level of resilience after returning to their homes, as well as a decreased sense of connection to their family and community. Lastly, Lcsw-C (2022) stated that dealing with melancholy or sadness can occasionally feel insurmountable yet making a small effort to practice mindful and purposeful behavior can have a significant positive effect.

Table 3 shows the level of students living in boarding houses when grouped according to sex (Male=6.96; Female=6.99, p-value 0.616). In the results, it is visible that there are no significant differences between coping self-efficacy and sex. Female students report higher average self-efficacy than male students, although all students report higher than average self-efficacy (Fahle et al. 2019).

The level of students living in boarding houses when grouped according to program cluster (CBA=6.94; COED=6.95; CAS=7.08, p-value 0.761) shows that there are no significant differences between coping self-efficacy and program cluster. According to the research, students who have a strong feeling of efficacy believe they can complete even challenging activities. In the face of certain failures, these students intensify and

sustain their efforts to succeed. They approach tough or dangerous circumstances with the assurance that they are in control of them (Fratturar, 2018).

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to ascertain the level of coping self-efficacy among students living in boarding houses at Kabankalan Catholic College. The results of the study shown that college students at Kabankalan Catholic College had a "moderately certain can do" level of coping self-efficacy. The College of Business and Accountancy has the lowest level of coping self-efficacy, whereas the College of Arts and Sciences has the highest level. When grouped according to sex, women outperform men in terms of having the highest level of coping self-efficacy. Additionally, the study's findings indicate that college students at Kabankalan Catholic College have a "moderately certain can-do" of coping self-efficacy, meaning they are left with no alternative but to adapt and become independent while living in a boarding house. It suggests that CSES is a useful tool for assessing the coping self-efficacy of students living in boarding houses. Furthermore, it could be drawn from the findings that more women are living in boarding houses as a result of the rise in the frequency of theft, rape, and other violent crimes in the Philippines, where women make up the majority of the victims. Women's parents prefer that they board because they believe that they are more vulnerable to risk and danger. Compared to males who typically don't need to be picked up when they go home at night. Additionally, our participants' spiritual fortitude in God is greater as demonstrated by their expression of faith through prayers. They turn to God for strength and guidance on a daily basis as they navigate life. Lastly, the College of Education has a large number of participants since, according to the students enrolled at Kabankalan Catholic College, COED has a large number of enrollees. This study made the following recommendation: In this case, the guidance office can offer emotional help, for their students, and teachers can serve as models of encouragement. Students will observe them and take note of the ways of coping they employ on a regular basis, as well as make the online consultation once a week, if possible. Students require support and attention for what they are going through and instruction in managing or boosting their coping self-efficacy.

Recommendations

It recommended that school administrators and the school's guidance office may create programs to address the problems of the students living in boarding houses, teachers are encouraged to be aware of what is happening, and students may experience issues at the boarding house, such as homesickness, loneliness and lack of emotional support. In these cases, the guidance office can offer emotional help, for their students, and teachers can serve as models of encouragement. Students will observe them and take note of the ways of coping they employ on a regular basis, as well as make the online consultation once a week, if possible. Students require support and attention for what they are going through and instruction in managing or boosting their

coping self-efficacy.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The obligation of the researchers to act for the benefit of the respondents and support several moral rules to protect and defend the rights of others, prevent harm, and remove conditions that will causes harm. The researcher provides sufficient information and assurances about taking part to allow participants to understand the implications of participation to reach a fully informed, considered, and freely given decision about whether to do so, without the exercise of any pressure or coercion. Preserving confidentiality and anonymity is included, the names and other details of the participants were kept a secret by the researcher.

No conflict was arisen while conducting the study. The researchers have reviewed the study to guarantee that there is no someone's work was plagiarized by the researcher. The researcher identifies the results with no bias, and the results are purely for research use only.

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